

ФИЛОЛОГИЯ, ИНОСТРАННЫЕ ЯЗЫКИ, ЖУРНАЛИСТИКА

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БРАНДАУСОВА Александра Вячеславовнастарший преподаватель, кандидат филологических наук,
Московский государственный университет им. М. В. Ломоносова, Россия, г. Москва

ФУНКЦИИ ПОЛИСИНДЕТОНА В ТЕКСТЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ К.С. ЛЬЮИСА «ЛЕВ, КОЛДУНЯ И ПЛАТЯНОЙ ШКАФ»

Аннотация. В статье исследуются функции полисиндетона в произведении К.С. Льюиса «Лев, колдунья и платяной шкаф». Выделяются ключевые роли этого стилистического приёма – от создания атмосферы до передачи символических смыслов. На примерах текстового анализа демонстрируется полифункциональность полисиндетона, который усиливает эмоциональное восприятие, ритм повествования и глубину характеристик персонажей.

Ключевые слова: полисиндетон, синтаксис, Хроники Нарнии.

Полисиндетон в тексте произведения «Лев, колдунья и платяной шкаф» К.С. Льюиса выполняет следующие основные функции:

1. **Атмосферообразующую** (создание зрительных, звуковых и сенсорных образов): «Presently the clouds parted overhead and the winter sun came out and the snow all around them grew dazzlingly bright» (Глава 6: «Into the Forest»)

2. **Эмоциональную** (передача чувств персонажей и настроения): «Up to that moment, Edmund had been feeling sick, and sulky, and annoyed with Lucy for being right, but he hadn't made up his mind what to do». (Глава 5: «Back on This Side of the Door».)

3. **Ритмообразующую** (имитация движения, звука или скорости движения): «Have you ever had a gallop on a horse? Think of that; and then take away the heavy noise of the hoofs and the jingle of the bit and imagine instead the almost noiseless padding of the great paws. Then imagine instead of the black or grey or chestnut back of the horse the soft roughness of golden fur, and the mane flying back in the wind. And then imagine you are going about twice as fast as the fastest racehorse. But this is a mount that doesn't need to

be guided and never grows tired. He rushes on and on, never missing his footing, never hesitating, threading his way with perfect skill between tree trunks, jumping over bush and briar and the smaller streams, wading the larger, swimming the largest of all. And you are riding not on a road nor in a park nor even on the downs, but right across Narnia, in spring, down solemn avenues of beech and across sunny glades of oak, through wild orchards of snow-white cherry trees, past roaring waterfalls and mossy rocks and echoing caverns, up windy slopes alight with gorse bushes, and across the shoulders of heathery mountains and along giddy ridges and down, down, down again into wild valleys and out into acres of blue flowers.» (Глава 15: «Deeper Magic from Before the Dawn of Time»)

4. **Символическую** (аллюзии на сакральные или философские темы): «And they entered into friendship and alliance with countries beyond the sea and paid them visits of state and received visits of state from them. (Глава 17: «The Hunting of the White Stag»)

5. **Детализирующую** (акцентирование важных элементов описания): «That was what the others chiefly noticed, but Edmund noticed

something else. A little lower down the river there was another small river which came down another small valley to join it. And looking up that valley, Edmund could see two small hills, and he was almost sure they were the two hills which the White Witch had pointed out to him when he parted from her at the lamp-post that other day. And then between them, he thought, must be her palace, only a mile off or less. And he thought about Turkish Delight and about being a King ("And I wonder how Peter will like that?" he asked himself) and horrible ideas came into his head». (Глава 7: «A Day with the Beavers»)

6. **Сенсорную** (описание тактильных/обонятельных/вкусовых ощущений): «It was something he had never tasted before, very sweet and foamy and creamy, and it warmed him right down to his toes». (Глава 1: «Turkish Delight»)

7. **Характеризации** (описание характеристик персонажей): «And Susan grew into a tall and gracious woman with black hair that fell almost to her feet and the kings of the countries beyond the sea began to send ambassadors asking for her hand in marriage. And she was called Queen Susan the Gentle». (Глава 17: «The Hunting of the White Stag»)

8. **Контактоустанавливающую** (обращение к читателю): «And now of course you want to know what had happened to Edmund» (Глава 9: «In the Witch House»)

Полисиндетон в произведении «Лев, колдунья и платяной шкаф» выполняет многоуровневые функции: от создания атмосферы до передачи эмоций и символического подтекста. Анализ произведения показал, что данное

синтаксическое средство выражения экспрессивности также часто полифункционально и может сочетать одновременно 2-3 и более функции. Полисиндетон у С.К. Льюиса является приемом многомерного повествования, подчеркивающим сказочную природу текста.

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BRANDAUSOVA Alexandra Vyacheslavovna
Senior Lecturer, Candidate of Philological Sciences,
Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia, Moscow

THE FUNCTIONS OF THE POLYSYNDETON IN THE TEXT OF THE WORK OF C.S. LEWIS "THE LION, THE WITCH AND THE WARDROBE"

Abstract. The article examines the functions of polysyndeton in the work of C.S. Lewis "The Lion, the Witch and the Wardrobe". The key roles of this stylistic device are highlighted, from creating an atmosphere to conveying symbolic meanings. The examples of text analysis demonstrate the polyfunctionality of the polysyndeton, which enhances emotional perception, the rhythm of narration and the depth of character characteristics.

Keywords: polysyndeton, syntax, Chronicles of Narnia.